

Can Risk Assessment Tools Produce Fair Outcomes in an Unfair Society?

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Abstract

Pretrial detention depends on weighing an unconvicted defendant’s right to freedom against the risk that defendant poses to the community. The prediction of future criminal activity lies at the heart of the justification of pretrial detention; however, both intuition and data suggest that such a prediction is difficult and prone to subjective bias. Using data from the 2018 Virginia Pretrial Data Project, we attempt to predict new violent criminal arrest using a variety of machine learning methods, and we compare our results with predictions from a far simpler tool, the Public Safety Assessment (PSA) from Arnold Ventures. We further explore alternative frameworks for algorithmic fairness when using these models as risk assessment tools and demonstrate inherent tradeoffs in competing definitions of fairness. We show that while the PSA does pass certain thresholds for algorithmic fairness, the implications of the competing definitions may not be evident to decision-makers. Our study emphasizes the current limitations of using risk assessment tools for pretrial decision-making and highlights the need for a multidisciplinary approach that considers alternatives to detention to protect public safety and respect the rights of defendants. The results of this study contribute to the ongoing discourse on the role of data-driven tools in the criminal justice system and underscore the need for comprehensive approaches to address systemic inequalities.

1 Introduction

We examine data from Virginia’s Pretrial Data Project for calendar year 2018. The data reflects some well-known disparities in criminal justice, with Black men dramatically over-represented versus their share of the population, for example. Within the data, however, the role of race becomes insignificant as a predictor for pretrial outcomes when controlling for various salient factors like indigency, age, pending charges and criminal history. While important work continues discovering drivers and impacts of the use of pretrial detention in

Virginia, we here look at a fundamental justification for the use of pretrial detention, risk of harm.

Preventative detention was ruled constitutional in *U.S. vs. Salerno* (1987) on the grounds that some defendants, like the notorious mobster, Risk determines the prediction of future criminal activity. Both intuition and data confirm that such a prediction is inherently difficult and prone to subjective bias. Algorithmic tools whose role is to assess risk from defendants have sought to bring a level of data-driven objectivity to pretrial decisions. We examine the potential of one popular tool, the Public Safety Assessment (PSA). This tool is not currently in use in Virginia, but the predictions from the tool are easily generated. We examine the tool against the data provided by the Virginia Pretrial Data Project (2018) and apply metrics for algorithmic fairness. We also compare the accuracy of the tool against a fully unconstrained model. We show that while the PSA does pass certain thresholds for algorithmic fairness, the use of the tool does require tradeoffs potentially invisible to decision makers. We further show that algorithmic fairness is insufficient for addressing entrenched disparities in society.

2 Related Work

Our work has benefited immensely from the hard work performed by the Virginia Criminal Sentencing Commission in collecting and making available the aggregated pretrial data for October 2017 in the initial release and the full 2018 calendar year. The collection involved coordination of numerous state agencies and cross-referencing arrest and court records to track defendants through the justice system. The commission is also to be commended for their continued efforts in updating the data set as new information becomes available such as amending data on Presumptive Denial of Bail as it became available. The commission’s report [1] provides important descriptive statistics but strongly emphasizes that they do not make claims of causal relationships among the reported factors nor do they make claims about the reasons for pretrial decisions.

The issue of fairness in criminal justice risk assessments

has been the subject of extensive research. Numerous studies have investigated the potential biases and unfairness associated with risk assessment tools, particularly with regards to their impact on minority groups and disadvantaged populations. We build on work by Berk et al. [3] examining six types of fairness in criminal justice risk assessments and evaluating their applications. Different scholars have employed different terminology for closely related or even identical measures depending on the use case. Prediction of an unwanted outcome like criminal recidivism is characterized as risk, while prediction of a desirable outcome like college admission or loan approval is discussed in terms of opportunity. In both cases, predictive algorithms need to be assessed for bias and fairness, and the same frameworks can apply, though the terminology may mask the underlying similarity. Berk helpfully collects these various terms into a unified set of ideas which can be meaningfully compared.

Finally, our work has involved a close examination of the Public Safety Assessment (PSA) from Arnold Ventures. The PSA is not currently part of pretrial decisions in Virginia, which uses its own risk assessment tool, the Virginia Pretrial Risk Assessment Instrument, or VPRAI. The PSA has an extensive and growing literature evaluating its use and potential, as well as its limitations. We build upon work from Andersen et al. [2] and DeMichele et al [6].

3 Our Approach

We do not engage in the contentious arguments about the retributive versus utilitarian purpose of criminal punishment except insofar as we focus solely on new violent criminal activity in the pretrial period as a justification for pretrial detention. A defendant who poses a substantial risk for violent crime can, we maintain, be detained even though there cannot be certainty about that defendant’s future crime. We therefore attempt to predict future violent criminal arrest using all available data a magistrate might have access to and train models unconstrained by obvious ethical objections to using membership in protected classes as a predictor. That is, we include all available demographic data such as a defendant’s race, sex, indigency status, and age, as well as locality information and census data. We investigate these unconstrained models to quantify impacts to accuracy and precision involved in the use or exclusion of protected class information, such as sex or race. This provides a useful comparandum with a tools which do not use these factors. We confirm what is already well-known, that while predicting the rate of crime in the aggregate is feasible, determining risk at the individual level remains incredibly difficult.

The PSA actually consists of three scores assessing the risk of a defendant for failure to appear in court (FTA), new criminal arrest (NCA), and new violent criminal arrest (NVCA). We focus only on the last as the most salient to decisions

about pretrial detention. The decision to deprive an unconvicted defendant of his or her freedom incurs real costs for the defendant and community, but those costs are weighed against the risk of harm from a dangerous defendant. [9] The NVCA score takes into account a defendant’s prior criminal history as well as age, but does not consider a defendant’s race, sex, wealth, or level of education. It does not attempt to quantify a defendant’s connections within the community or prior drug use. The tool uses a discrete scale of features easily calculated for most defendants, and the tool, in contrast to Virginia’s own risk assessment tool (VPRAI), does not require an interview with the defendant.

New arrest for violent crime during the pretrial period is rare. The pretrial detention data from 2018 reveals that the rate of new violent criminal arrest is approximately 2.2 percent. However, we must acknowledge that the observed rate comes from a population of defendants of whom 7.1% have been denied pretrial release. Within the detained population, the rate of new violent arrest is even lower, around 1%, since these defendants presumably have limited opportunity to face a new violent criminal arrest while in custody. Critics could argue that the rate of new violent arrest is only as low as it is after the riskiest defendants have been detained. We do not have access to an experimental design to test the counterfactual within the available data, but to account for these two distinct populations with different rates of new violent criminal arrest, we set aside those detained for now to focus on the 93% of defendants who were not detained pretrial. This provides a substantial population of 329,505 defendants.

Figure 1

As we will see in Figure 1, those presenting the highest risk under the PSA, but who were not detained pretrial, show a rate of new violent criminal arrest near 10%, in contrast with defendants with the lowest scores who show a less than 1% rate of new violent arrest. The goal is to find predictors which allow us to identify as many of those new offenders while

minimizing our false positives, that is, defendants flagged as high-risk who do not go on to have a new violent arrest.

The data available include many aspects of defendants’ lives. We are not working within a defined sociological theory of recidivism, and thus we have no basis on which to limit the number or kind of interactions which should be considered. As such, we do not attempt to engineer a sufficiently rich but not arbitrarily large feature space. Rather than exploring these permutations, likely fruitlessly, we chose to train ensembles of tree models which capture these effects inherently. In particular, we trained a random forest and a model of gradient boosted trees on two versions of the training data balanced using downsampling and SMOTE sampling.

We employed downsampling on the training set by using all of the minority class, here defendants who have a subsequent violent arrest, and a random sample of equal size from the majority class. This approach gives us an even split between positive and negative cases, so the model has to discriminate on the basis of those features rather than simply “cheating” by learning the lopsided distribution. Downsampling has the unfortunate effect that we leave aside a large portion of our potential training data, and in fact in our case our training data becomes smaller than our test data. As such, our models are potentially undertrained.

We also apply a separate approach known as SMOTE sampling [4] to generate synthetic data which echoes the distribution of the minority class. We thus achieve a balanced, and large data set on which to train the models. This approach yields much more data, but a great deal of that data is not “real”, per se, and so aspects of the minority class may get overstated simply due to sampling.

In cleaning the data for analysis we strove to retain as much data as possible. Most of the data is categorical which we one-hot encoded, including categories for which the VCSC indicated that data was missing. The numeric data primarily consists of prior criminal records. Most defendants have zero or very few prior arrests, while a small number of individuals have high numbers. This extreme right skew to the data hinders the model’s ability to find patterns. We settled on a universal solution in which we generated normalized values for each numeric column, applied the inverse hyperbolic sine (ihs), which pulls in large values in a manner similar to a log transformation but which can handle zero values, and we created a normalized version of the ihs. Models were given both the original skewed data as well as all three transformations for all numeric variables. The accuracy and F1 scores of these models are reported below:

Model	Accuracy	F1-Score
RF-Downsampled	0.66	0.10
RF-SMOTE	0.81	0.12
BT-Downsampled	0.72	0.13
BT-SMOTE	0.98	0.01
PSA_NVCA Flag	0.94	0.10

RF = Random Forest, BT = Boosted Trees

We call attention to a few remarkable features of these results. First, the most accurate model of all is the Boosted tree model using SMOTE sampling. This model used upsampling to create a large training set in which half of the observations had a new violent criminal arrest. The gradient boosted tree model is computationally expensive, but after training achieved 98% accuracy. That accuracy results from virtually always predicting no. We can see this in the confusion matrix for the boosted model using SMOTE on our test set:

	Pred:No NVCA	Pred:NVCA
True:No NVCA	69,200	163
True:NVCA	1,551	8

Even though the model was trained on a completely balanced data set, it only predicts a tiny fraction of defendants will have a new violent arrest, and its accuracy within those predictions is very poor. The model misses virtually all of the true NVCA cases. We highlight this model to underscore the difficulty in making accurate predictions of future arrest. The model is manifestly terrible, yet the number of defendants falsely flagged is very low in comparison to other models, even though the proportion of false positives to true positives is very high. Given how different the proportions of predictions are on the test set versus the training set, it is interesting to examine which features were driving these predictions. In every one of the models, the number one feature driving the decisions of the trees is indigency status. Within this data, indigency is defined simply in terms of the use of a private attorney versus a court appointed attorney or public defender. While it is important to note that feature importance in the ensemble is not the same as a large coefficient in a regression and does not reflect whether the feature drove predictions toward or away from a positive prediction, the basket of features can be illustrative of how the model is deriving its results. The Random Forest with SMOTE sampling achieved the highest accuracy while maintaining a reasonable F1 score, at least among these models, and so we examine here the features the model used the most:

Figure 2

We see the clear prominence of indigency as a factor in the model, as both levels of the category drive the decisions. The other notable fact is that this model places importance on the PSA_NVCA criteria, picking out the feature directly in total points, as well as a transformations of that score. This would seem to indicate that the basket of features within the PSA do carry at least some predictive power.

In our attempts to use a “kitchen sink” approach to predicting new violent criminal arrest, we were unable to surpass the accuracy of the PSA_NVCA without giving up actual predictive power, resulting in interesting but wholly unusable models. While we have models which achieve slightly better F1 scores than the PSA_NVCA, these models include data on protected class membership, as well as predictors simply encoding the absence of a predictor, which would be inappropriate in a real risk assessment tool. Other combinations of features or different weighting of those features could produce even better performance than the PSA_NVCA, but we did not find such a combination. We instead now turn to a look at the definitions and measures of algorithmic fairness currently in use to evaluate the PSA_NVCA versus our models.

4 Algorithmic Fairness

There is a rich and expansive literature regarding fairness in algorithmic decision making. This discussion proceeds on numerous axes including the need for transparency, accountability, accuracy, equity, and others. Our inquiry builds primarily on the framing of Berk et al. [REF-Risk assessment state of the art], who collects the most prominent definitions, helpfully combining those definitions which have been employed under different names. We briefly detail the definitions we apply to our models and demonstrate the tradeoffs involved in attempting to achieve different measures of fairness.

Overall accuracy equality refers to the extent to which the tool produces equally accurate outcomes for different groups in the population. **Statistical parity** considers the extent to which the tool produces similar outcomes for different groups in the population. **Conditional procedure accuracy equality** measures the extent to which the risk assessment tool produces equally accurate outcomes for the different groups in the population, conditional on the true outcome. This measure corresponds to “equalized odds” or “error rate balance” in other work. **Conditional use accuracy equality** compares the accuracy of the outcomes conditional on predicted outcome by the tool on different groups. **Treatment equality** compares the ratio of false negatives to false positives among different groups to assess whether individuals are treated similarly. This can be instructive when looking at a single model, but it does not use a scale that allows comparison of different models. **Total Fairness** is the state where all five previous forms of fairness are achieved; Berk provides a proof that that total fairness is impossible when base rates differ between protected groups. [3]

To illustrate the meanings and implications of these measurements, we present a breakdown for the PSA_NVCA Flag versus occurrences of new violent criminal arrest for defendants who were released pretrial. Defendants who were detained pretrial are not comparable in this evaluation, though clearly they are a population of great interest. The Flag labels a defendant as high-risk for new criminal arrest if they have a PSA_NVCA score above 4. We begin with a confusion matrix for all released defendants:

PSA_NVCA Flag for Released Defendants		
	Pred:No NVCA	Pred:NVCA
True:No NVCA	311254	10707
True:NVCA	6438	1106

This model achieves 94.8% accuracy with an F1 score of .11. It misses nearly six times as many true new violent arrests as it gets right, and it incorrectly flags nearly ten times as many people as high-risk as it correctly predicts. These misclassifications are reflected in the F1 score which, while objectively low, compares favorably with other risk assessments and our own models. To assess the tool for algorithmic fairness, we next choose a protected class and evaluate the performance of the tool on groups within that class. While the role of race is deeply concerning in criminal justice, for our purposes comparing men and women is more instructive because the base rates for new violent arrest differ more, and we can see these effects reflected in measures of fairness. For released defendants, we find rates of new violent arrest of 2.41% for men and 1.74% for women. We now look at predictions for these groups separately:

PSA_NVCA Flag for Released Women		
	Pred:No NVCA	Pred:NVCA
True:No NVCA	108805	2450
True:NVCA	1759	211

PSA_NVCA Flag for Released Men		
	Pred:No NVCA	Pred:NVCA
True:No NVCA	223035	11941
True:NVCA	4858	957

These confusion matrices allow us to more easily compare how the tool predicts across groups. First, in terms of statistical parity, we compare the proportion of the whole group who are flagged as high risk or low risk. These proportions sum to one, so we need only consider a single measure. In this case, 2.4% of women are flagged, while 5.3% of men are flagged, showing a three point spread. With populations this large that difference is significant, and thus the PSA_NVCA might be said to be unfair on the basis of Statistical Parity. That would be a flawed argument to level at the tool, however, as the difference derives at least partially from the different base rates of new criminal arrest between men and women, so calibrating the tool to increase the proportion of women

flagged would be at odds with reality. Moreover, attempts to adjust a tool to optimize this metric can lead to highly undesirable outcomes for individuals [3]. As a comparandum, our highly accurate but non-predictive Boosted SMOTE model achieves nearly perfect Statistical Parity simply by flagging vanishingly few defendants of each category.

Conditional use accuracy equality, also known as **predictive parity**, [5] asks whether a tool produces equivalent accuracy across two different groups conditional on the predicted outcome. That is, when the tool predicts high-risk among men and among women, this metric compares what proportion of those predictions are correct. This is not a binary comparison for positive and negative predictions, and so we should consider both in assessing whether a tool performs well on this metric. In our case, the PSA_NVCA predicts a defendant is high-risk with 7.4% precision for men and 7.9% precision for women. For negative predictions we find 97.9% accuracy for men and 98.4% accuracy for women. In each case, the accuracy rates differ by only half a percentage point, and thus the PSA_NVCA does well on this metric. For some scholars, predictive parity is indicative that a tool is “well-calibrated,” though discussions of requirements for model calibration sometimes require a probability score rather than a binary prediction to meet the standard of being well-calibrated. [8]

Conditional use accuracy equality does allow us to compare across models and can be achieved even when the base rate varies across groups. We are examining not how accurate the model’s predictions are but whether the model is equally successful at predicting without regard to which group a defendant belongs. Looking again at our accuracy when predicting a defendant is high risk, the PSA_NVCA only gets less than 8% of those positive predictions right, but this rate is consistent whether it is predicting for men or women. Coincidentally, this proportion is similar when comparing between Black and White defendants, where the respective rates are 7.9% and 7.1% for Black and White defendants, respectively. As such, we do find a measure on which the PSA_NVCA can make a claim to a well-recognized metric of algorithmic fairness.

An individual flagged as high-risk by a tool with almost 95% accuracy still only has a less than 8% chance of having a new violent criminal arrest. The bar for how high that threshold should be is a matter of policy and discussions of algorithmic fairness do not provide definitive answers. Rather, the metrics can drive decision makers to consider thoughtfully the implications of using a tool for risk mitigation. A brief look at facts from the pretrial data can be instructive as to the uses and limits of risk assessments. We here look at identical data from Figure 1, presented with fuller context with Figure 3.

Figure 3

Figures 1 and 3 both show the rate of new violent arrest for defendants who were not detained pretrial according to their risk scores on the PSA_NVCA. Figure 1 highlights that increasing scores do correlate with increased incidence of new violent arrest. Figure 3, however, shows exactly the same thing but includes the context that even at the highest scores, the proportion of defendants who go on to have a new violent criminal arrest in the pretrial period is low and denying pretrial release to all defendants with high risk scores will necessarily involve detaining far more defendants than could reasonably be expected to experience a new violent arrest. These proportions do not tell the whole story, however. There are far fewer defendants with high scores than low scores. Thus even with low rates of new violent arrests, the majority of new violent criminal arrests come from defendants with scores of 2 or below.

Figure 4

These are challenging policy decisions, since choosing to detain defendants with scores below three means detaining

people with less than a 5% chance of a new violent criminal arrest. Nonetheless, in Virginia, that is often the case. The current state of pretrial detention is summed up in this chart which shows the distribution of risk scores for defendants detained and released pretrial.

Figure 5

While the detained population has proportionally higher membership from the higher risk classes, the majority, indeed almost 60%, do have a risk score of 2 or below. While we acknowledge the caveats in relying too heavily on this metric, we do feel that Virginia can make progress in reducing its use of pretrial detention without materially damaging public safety by increasing the bar for detention to focus primarily on only the riskiest defendants. While not a perfect solution, risk assessment tools like the PSA_NVCA do support less frequent detention when used judiciously and in concert with a magistrate’s judgment and experience.

5 Conclusion

Predicting a defendant’s risk of future violent arrest remains imprecise, and mistaken predictions have consequences for defendants and their communities. Risk assessment tools must be transparent and continually monitored for disparate impact. While the PSA_NVCA does show some attractive features regarding its performance on some definitions of fairness, the tool can only address one point in the criminal justice pipeline. More work is needed to better understand the effects of pretrial detention on defendants and communities beyond the pretrial period, as well as the drivers of arrest. Our models all showed indigency status as an important feature in predicting new violent criminal arrest. Indigency here reflects the use of a private attorney versus a public defender or court appointed lawyer. Access to meaningful counsel at first appearance, a feature not present in our data, has the potential to level the playing field for defendants as they face their pretrial

decision. Virginia is currently beginning a multi-jurisdiction randomized-control trial to examine the costs, benefits, and impact of providing continuous access to counsel beginning at initial appearance. [7] Good data on these important questions can lead to a more just Virginia.

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